

Open Life Science Proposal for *Seeds to Systems* - Developed for CZI

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Background

The persistent inequities in funding access, compounded by language barriers and unequal collaborations among researchers across countries, exacerbate the economic and scientific divide. This disparity particularly affects underrepresented and minority groups globally, limiting their participation in research. Limited local funding options and

unfamiliarity with international funding norms and skills, often due to language, cultural, and access barriers, disproportionately disadvantage researchers in low-resource settings in both Low- to Middle-Income countries (LMICs) and High-Income Countries (HICs).

The imbalance in collaborations is further amplified when funders allocate resources for international collaboration without adequate support for potential applicants lacking experience in managing funding or engaging in multi-stakeholder collaborations. Researchers are expected to intuitively create competitive research plans, know how to make compelling arguments for prioritizing local challenges in international contexts, set up financial and legal infrastructure to manage the funding and demonstrate 'tacit' leadership skills (often without having a possibility to develop them). The lack of appropriate opportunities to develop these skills and experiences hinders researchers' ability to leverage funding opportunities to advance and sustain their research or to work effectively with other teams or organizations in a horizontal and non-subordinate collaboration. This lack of previous experience and infrastructure support for navigating social dynamics leads to wasted time, resource depletion without achieving research impact, and, in the worst cases, frustration, burnout, dismissal, or exclusion of marginalized stakeholders.

The absence of adequate training, mentoring, and infrastructure support remains a significant barrier for researchers impacted by these inequities, limiting their participation in co-designing the scientific landscape.

Program Overview

The [OLS \(Open Life Science\)](#) team proposes an advanced cohort-based training and coaching focused on essential **competencies and skills needed to navigate the research funding landscape**, along with access to fiscal sponsorship infrastructure for sustainable management of research projects. Referred to as the '**Seeds to Systems' Program**, this project builds upon the success of OLS's cohort-based training and mentoring program, known as [Open Seeds](#). Since its establishment in 2019, OLS has [delivered eight cohorts](#), engaging over 500 learners and practitioners who have worked on nearly 300 projects worldwide (over 70 countries). We have seen the transformative impact of our approach, especially for members from underrepresented minority groups, who have greatly benefited from expert mentoring, peer-based knowledge exchange, and curated opportunities for professional development and funding, both during and beyond their participation in OLS programs

Through the Seeds to Systems, we proposed an extension to the OLS services, aiming to level the playing field for researchers and teams applying for funding to advance their research projects. With a goal to advance and sustain research with open source/science solutions in biomedical and related fields, we will offer specialized training to researchers, especially those from underrepresented groups and LMICs. The Seeds to Systems will contribute to advancing research through funding, guidance on maintenance and mentored support on ensuring the sustainability of research outcomes in a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) manner. Leveraging the open science network and partners of OLS, this program will engage practitioners,

collaborators, and communities openly, making knowledge, expertise, collaboration and opportunities around funding open and accessible.

The main project activities encompass: **i)** developing the 'OLS Seeds to Systems Curriculum', **ii)** providing cohort-based specialized training and structured coaching to community leaders to enhance their skills and potential to build competitive and fundable research proposals, **iii)** offering organizational infrastructure, such as through fiscal sponsorship and access to finance management and legal expertise, particularly in the initial stages of project management, **iv)** carrying out research-based impact assessment along with the methodological collection of feedback data from participants to understand and improve the program in an iterative manner.

Throughout the development and delivery of this program, OLS will establish partnerships with local and international experts through resident fellowship, community engagement opportunities and formal collaborations.

We will develop on the existing 'Hidden Curriculum' co-designed by contributors, many representing different communities at the [NumFOCUS Diversity & Inclusion in Scientific Computing conference](#). Although open science curriculum will be primarily developed and delivered in English, coaching, mentoring and expert consultation will be made available in different languages and contexts as represented by the diverse stakeholders in the OLS community. There will also be opportunities to translate and localize resources in the preferred language of our learners, which will be shared openly for others to use.

Scope of the Target Audience

Although this proposal was initially designed for researchers currently working at institutions in LMICs, researchers from underrepresented groups, such as historically marginalized groups in high-income countries, black colleges and universities in the USA, or other minority-serving institutions across the Global North and the global Majority will also benefit from such training. The curriculum will be developed with these diverse audiences in mind, an area where the involvement of diverse resident fellows and the community will play a key co-creation role. As such, we will consider applications from researchers from these target groups from or residing in both LMICs, as well as HICs.

OLS is committed to fostering stronger representation of researchers from minority groups, creating opportunities for them to establish themselves as experts and leaders in international research and funding landscapes. Leveraging our successful approach to cohort-based training and mentoring in Open Seeds, we will support researchers ready to take their next step in research leadership.

The impact of this initiative will also be assessed systematically and communicated openly, disseminating evidence, examples, impact stories and case studies from this project.

Work Packages, Outcomes and Key Deliverables

Work Packages

The project will be developed under five work packages (WP), each focused on different aspects of the initiative.

- **WP-1:** Development of the Seeds to Systems curriculum, also mentioned as "WP-1-Curriculum"
- **WP-2:** Delivering the curriculum through cohort training, mentioned below as "WP-2-cohort"
- **WP-3:** Transitioning to a new financial model through Fiscal Sponsorship, also mentioned as "WP-3-FS"
- **WP-4:** Impact assessments through community-based research, also mentioned as "WP-4-Research"
- **WP-5:** Project and community management, also mentioned as "WP-5-PM"

The project spans two years, divided into several phases, each with specific deliverables to ensure progress and accountability.

Expected Outcomes

1. **O1: Increased access to high-quality training and curriculum:** with a goal of empowering researchers with the skills, networks, and resources needed to refine and improve their grant proposals, and enhance their ability to secure funding (**WP-1**)
2. **O2: Successful delivery of cohort-based training:** with participants acquiring critical knowledge, skills, and confidence in developing their research grant proposals, identifying suitable funding opportunities, and managing their projects successfully (**WP-2**)
3. **O3: Iterative improvement of the training program:** through real-world testing, resulting in a highly effective curriculum. Participant satisfaction and engagement will be measured through regular feedback and successful learning outcomes, ensuring the program meets the needs of its audience (**WP-1, WP-2**)
4. **O4: Strengthened OLS infrastructure for fiscal sponsoring capability:** with developed and realized business models for onboarding, supporting and transitioning the organizations to self-sustaining entities. This will be coupled with an expanded partnership network with other fiscal sponsors to efficiently support for diverse projects across various regions (**WP-3**)
5. **O5: High-quality support for research projects from low-resource and underrepresented groups:** through training, mentoring, coaching and fiscal sponsoring infrastructure in securing and managing funding, particularly during their crucial initial stages (**WP-2, WP-3**)
6. **O6: Tangible impact on participants:** through research-based assessment, tangible impact will be evidenced by successful grant submissions by the graduates of OLS, funding of new projects led by graduates, and enhanced career opportunities for all involved (**WP-4**)
7. **O7: Enhanced OLS reputation:** through quality and reliable service we will

establish OLS as a leading supporter of research initiatives, especially in under-served and low-resource regions. This will result in increased interest, broader impact, and greater participation in OLS programs, laying a strong foundation for future funding and expansion **(WP-4)**

8. **O8: Widespread adoption of the Seeds to Systems:** through OLS-offered services, funder-supported cohort delivery, and collaborations with partnering organizations dedicated to supporting researchers in their communities. This will leverage resident fellows, the existing global community of OLS and collaborators who will be actively involved in the program, ensuring its sustainability and scalability beyond its initial scope. **(WP-5)**

Underlying all these outcomes will be effective project management supported by the key personnel involved in the scoping, implementation and delivery of all work packages **(WP-5)**.

The engagement of research fellows in different packages will diversify the curriculum content, modes of cohort delivery and scaling capacity, while taking local and contextual knowledge of the target audience into account **(WP-1, WP-2, WP-4)**.

All of these outcomes will serve as key indicators of the program's success and long-term value. The program will continuously evolve to meet the specific needs of the participants and their projects. OLS will continue to **foster a vibrant community of practice** where graduates, resident fellows and contributors (including future candidates for the curriculum, Open Seeds and fiscal hosting opportunities) will benefit from peer support, mentorship, and the exchange of best practices.

Key Deliverables

1. **D1: Development of the Seeds to Systems curriculum:** with accessible program-specific information, training materials, and resources for the Seeds to Systems project in an accessible format. **(WP-1, O1, O3)**
 - Workshops and focus groups to develop Seeds to Systems curriculum and related materials.
 - Onboarding of expert practitioners and Research Fellows to support engagement from the community in ongoing development, feedback and continuous improvement of the Seeds to Systems curriculum.
 - Open source and publicly accessible repository on GitHub and website with curriculum modules, lesson plans, training videos, and resource guides. (CC-BY).
 - Regular updates to the repository with new materials and improvements based on feedback and evolving needs.
2. **D2: Delivering the curriculum through cohort training:** for participants, with the incorporation of lessons from feedback. **(WP-2, O1, O2, O3, O4)**
 - Pilot delivery and feedback integration in the Seeds to Systems curriculum, focusing on testing the materials and approach while actively engaging with the community for feedback.
 - collection and analysis of participant feedback through surveys, focus groups, and direct interactions with a diverse cohort of participants.

- Documentation of the pilot process, feedback and lessons learned. Refinement of curriculum and teaching methods based informing the full program rollout.
 - Recruitment of participants for the first cohort in close collaboration with funders
 - Delivery of the complete training program, including workshops, coaching sessions, and mentorship opportunities.
 - Ongoing assessment and support for participants throughout the program.
 - Reporting of participant outcomes, testimonials, and research-based program impact data.
3. **D3: Transitioning to a new financial model through Fiscal Sponsorship:** to support projects originating from low-resource settings. **(WP-3; O4, O5, O7)**
- Strengthening of OLS's Fiscal Sponsoring infrastructure through pilot community projects.
 - Development of financial and administrative support mechanisms tailored to the needs of low-resource projects.
 - Implementation of a streamlined process for fiscal sponsorship to handle and manage a larger number of community projects (described above).
4. **D4: Impact assessments through community-based research:** using qualitative and quantitative data. **(WP-4; O6, O8)**
- Scoping and planning qualitative/quantitative research.
 - Focus group/stakeholder workshop design and delivery
 - Reporting of impact and feedback in improving curriculum, cohort and fiscal sponsoring services.
 - Supporting the adoption of the resources and Seeds to Systems program in different contexts through collaboration and service-based delivery of training and access to fiscal hosting infrastructure..

In line with the OLS's current operations, we will remain committed to community engagement and open sharing of all outputs, while creating sustainability of the program.

- We will develop a structured community engagement strategy across all work packages and deliverables. It will include community roles such as for resident fellows, curriculum developers and participants with diverse expertise and backgrounds.
- We will publish all curriculum materials, program outcomes, and related resources under an open license.
- Our dissemination strategy will include webinars, workshops, and online campaigns to promote the use of program resources.
- We will maintain community support infrastructure to assist teams and organizations, especially in low-resource settings, in adopting and adapting the Seeds to Systems project materials.
- We will regularly update our partners and community on program developments and create opportunities for their involvement.

Cohort-Based Training and Curriculum

OLS has both the expertise and infrastructure necessary to effectively deliver the Seeds to Systems.

Experience with moving cohorts of learners: Over the last five years, the OLS team has proven their expertise in designing and delivering high-quality cohort-based curricula with evidence-based pedagogical methods for open science best practices and related training. The infrastructure set up for Open Seeds, OLS's flagship cohort-based program, which was incubated from Mozilla Open Leadership, will serve as the foundation for the Seeds to Systems.

A thriving community of researchers and open science experts: Since 2020, a large proportion of OLS learners, mentors and collaborators have remained engaged, often returning as mentors, speakers, facilitators, and even collaborators in organizing and delivering impactful training. These diverse members have become an important part of the community-based approach to our work, bringing real-world examples from their research and individual contexts. As experienced open science practitioners, they offer coaching, mentoring and timely support to our learners and participants.

Demand and interest in OLS's training and mentoring programs have been reflected in the success of Open Seeds through engagement and support from our learners, educators, mentors and partners. This continuous partnership has led to a consistent influx of new members and collaborators into the OLS community (*details and examples provided in Capability to Deliver*).

Preparatory work for the OLS Seeds to Systems Curriculum: We have actively collaborated in stewarding the community-led development of a 'Hidden Curriculum,' serving as a foundational resource for expanding the materials necessary for delivering this curriculum (<https://github.com/open-life-science/knowhow/pull/1/files>).

We have gauged interest and engagement from OLS's open science expert community, as well as non-profit organizations and funders, who have responded positively to this initiative and will be appropriately involved at various stages of the project. To support the learners of this project, we will leverage our existing resources, including fellowship opportunities, organizational materials, grant applications, policies, information management systems, governance resources, templates, training videos, projects developed by cohort members, and our diverse community. Consistent with our current practice, all resources developed by OLS will be openly shared under permissive licenses, with active support for adoption and reuse.

Transitioning from grant-based to service-based financial model: Over the years, we have also successfully transitioned our programs from grant-funded to paid consulting services, making cohort-based training such as Open Seeds a financially viable and stable offering from OLS (*details and examples provided in Capability to Deliver*).

OLS's existing projects and services serve as working models that can be readily adapted to ensure the successful delivery of the Seeds to Systems cohort and achieve financial sustainability for the project.

Fiscal Sponsorship Plan

Foundational Work for the Fiscal Sponsorship

OLS has been actively working to establish infrastructure to support smaller non-profit communities through fiscal sponsorship, which will remain a priority in this project. Currently, we are piloting the programme with three grassroots communities led by graduates from OLS who are actively working with their communities, developing their scaling plans and seeking funding to sustain their work: RSE Asia (in development), Open Phytoliths (in-principle sponsorship agreement in place), and RSE AU-NZ ([first official sponsored community](#)).

Scalability Plan through the Seeds to Systems

Anticipated journey mapping for fiscally hosted communities

Figure: Journey mapping for communities fiscally sponsored in OLS

1. Entry point (month 0):

- Graduation from the Seeds to Systems Cohorts, followed by research grants successfully acquired by candidates, will make them ideal for the OLS's fiscal sponsorship services. **We plan to deliver one cohort of the Seeds to Systems per year.**
- Eligibility for projects and communities will also be considered for relatively mature projects graduating from a previous cohort of OLS's Open Seeds. **We plan to deliver one cohort of OLS Open Seeds per year.**
- Assessment for new candidates will also be possible through service-based and grant-based partnerships with communities and through funder-suggested candidates from specific target communities/groups.

2. Onboarding (months 3-5):

- Onboarding will involve the suitability of the project, potential for legal and financial obligations to be met by the candidates and required due diligence as part of the onboarding process.
- Different onboarding paths will be developed for projects and organizations at different stages of development.
- A 1-3-year strategic plan will be developed for each project, with clear plans for possible financial sustainability pathways.
- By the end of this grant, we expect to have a fully developed service-based model to onboard subsequent cohorts of fiscally sponsored

communities.

3. Ongoing support and services (months 6-24)

- a. Communities will be offered different levels of support through **tier-based service and cost-sharing models**, enabling OLS to accommodate more organizations at varying stages.
- b. We will have clear project-based financial reporting and forecasting in place for each community - something not all current fiscal sponsors in the space can offer, but sorely wished for, based on our early market research.
- c. fundraising assistance and compliance management.

4. Transition (months 24-36)

- a. Organizations/communities might graduate to become an independent entity or exit the OLS's fiscal hosting status.
- b. Key milestones, impact, challenges and risk indicators will be developed as part of this proposal to assess and adapt the fiscal hosting relationship.
- c. We will **offboard larger communities** as they grow their own independence and transition to self-led organizations.

Strengthening of the fiscal hosting business model

This grant will allow us to develop and iterate on a robust monitoring and impact assessment framework to track the success of the pilot communities. Criteria and rubrics for all stages will be developed as part of our business development plans. A strengthened infrastructure will allow the handling of a higher number of projects, ensuring that the fiscal model can scale without compromising the quality of support.

Success will not merely be assessed in terms of a financial or publication-based metric, but also involve qualitative assessment and a community's specific vision. Insights will be used to refine our administrative support, legal services, and financial management capacity required for expanding the program through the Seeds to Systems. We will use this opportunity to better understand and optimize our operational costs and invest in business development to streamline the management of fiscally hosted communities, allowing OLS to support future cohorts with the same resources.

This model is likely to appeal to research funders who are looking to help grow/mature early-stage projects into a "fundable" profile, as well as incubator/accelerator programs that may provide financial backing and or in-kind support for future cohorts. As shared for Open Seeds, this will not be the first time we have transitioned grant-based funding into a service-led model. Open Seeds. Previously funded by CZI, Open Seeds is currently being offered in-house for the [Digital Research Alliance Canada as a service for grantees](#) (detailed in Capability to Deliver).

Partnership with other Fiscal hosts

Going forward, we will also establish formal reciprocal partnerships with organizations that offer fiscal hosting services in other countries for similar target audiences. This will allow us to co-develop shared infrastructure where possible, access a broader international funding market, and support the transition of communities out of OLS when

necessary.

Feedback and future improvement

Target outreach to specific groups and underserved areas where the impact of fiscal sponsorship would be most effective will allow the program to grow in a mission-led and impactful manner. Feedback mechanisms with participating communities will be used to improve the model while keeping the number of participating communities manageable and sustainable.

Year 1 and Year 2 Delivery of Work Packages

OLS Masterclass Project Timeline	Year 1 (Nov 2024 - Nov 2025)												Year 2 (Nov 2025 - Oct 2026)												
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Projected start date 1 March 2025	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	
WP 1 - Curriculum: Project scoping and onboarding project team	x	x																							
WP 1 - Curriculum: Project Kick-off, curriculum development		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x													
WP 2 - Curriculum: Curriculum test delivery								x	x	x	x	x	x	x											
WP 3 - Financial Infrastructure: Infrastructure need assessment - external - research funding landscape, gaps and opportunities for LMIC				x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x											
WP 3 - Financial Infrastructure: Infrastructure need assessment - Internal - Fiscal Sponsorship, revenue stream, diversifying	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x													
WP 1 - Curriculum open/peer review													x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x					
WP 2 - Cohort: Curriculum delivery for the first cohort																		x	x	x	x	x			
WP 3 - Financial Infrastructure: Legal and financial set up													x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
WP 3 - Financial Infrastructure made available																x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
WP 4 - Impact assessment and research													x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				
Reporting and strategy for scaling											x	x										x	x	x	
Check row: number of activities	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	3	3	4	5	5	5	5	4	3	2	2

Figure: 2-year timeline with anticipated duration for each work package. Using the start date for 1 November 2024, the third row shows months between November 2024 to November 2026.

Year 1: Piloting the Project

Months 1-3 (WP-1-Curriculum, WP-5-PM)

Objective: Project scoping and onboarding the project team

Activities

- Setting up project infrastructure
- Recruitment of the project team
- Contract setting for all involved
- Expert and fellow recruitment details

Outputs

- A public-facing website to report on the progress
- A public repository to ensure that the project is developed openly from the start
- Fellows and expert recruitment calls are announced

In the first year, we will recruit two research fellows - see the [role description for both roles](#).

The Research Fellows will collect and analyze both qualitative and quantitative data. Data will be gathered from published works, community interviews, workshops, and focus groups, with the scope and plan determined by project needs.

- They will establish the research roadmap, incorporating plans for community engagement, research communication, and impact assessment.
- Research participants in workshops and interviews will be engaged through well-considered questions to facilitate effective data collection.
- They will establish informed consent and clear terms of participation before data collection, with a commitment to FAIR data sharing principles.
- The research roadmap, necessary tooling, goals, and methodology will be agreed upon with the project team and advisors as needed.

Months 4-6 (WP-1-Curriculum, WP-5-PM)

Objective: Project kick-off

Activities

- Establishing a review and advisory committee
- Inviting community members with relevant expertise to join different WPs under various community roles
- Recruitment of resident fellow for 2) research-based curriculum development, 2) mapping research funding and sustainability ecosystem (to supplement the curriculum and support the feasibility study for OLS's Fiscal Hosting infrastructure).
- Kick-off and regular meeting with the project team
- Research for curriculum design, topic selection and content development will begin at this phase
- Landscape mapping begins for research funding and the sustainability ecosystem
- Both fellows will plan to involve community input and engagement, and plan stakeholder workshops as part of their research
- Both fellows will also engage with each other to provide peer-to-peer support and align their work as needed to reduce redundancy and ensure efficient use of shared resources

Outputs

- Creation of Ways of Working for all involved
- Landscape mapping resources, presented in a browsable and reusable manner
- The curriculum plan is shared based on research-based scoping and initial suggestions from the "hidden curriculum", inviting community input and

collaboration

Months 7-12 (WP-1-Curriculum, WP-1-Cohort, WP-3-FS)

Objective: Curriculum development and testing of fiscal sponsorship:

Activities:

- Fellows will lead the development of resources under their respective research with a goal to deliver the pilot cohort under WP-2 by the end of 12 months
- For WP-1, theme-based groups will be formed by onboarding experts selected through open calls, who will engage with the curriculum and resource development
- In WP-3, a small cohort with 3-5 projects will be established to understand the needs of the community for fiscal sponsorship. The cohort will include international projects to test the applicability of resources in both contexts
- For WP-2, a call for the first cohort will invite 15-20 research groups
- For WP-2, expert consultants, mentors and coaches will be identified to work with the cohort members for 6 months

Outputs

- A report will be developed sharing all outcomes, informing how the first cohort will be delivered through WP-1 and what services under the fiscal sponsorship will be provided under WP-3
- Outputs from this phase, as well as outcomes from the cohort engagement, will be communicated openly, marking the beginning of WP-4

Year 2: Scaling up, refining, and expanding the project

Months 13-21 (WP-1-Curriculum, WP-2-Cohort)

Objective: Refining and delivering the revised materials for the first open cohort

Activities

1. At the beginning of the second year, a community review will be opened (WP-1)
2. The curriculum will be shared, and a larger cohort training will be delivered with the support of trainers and experts (WP-2)
3. Research funding and sustainability information will be shared openly and used as a reference for the curriculum and the Fiscal hosting programme of OLS
4. Fiscal sponsorship infrastructure will be made available to support graduates preparing to apply for funding (for grantees external to the USA)
5. A debrief from the cohort delivery will be conducted with all participants involved in the project

Outputs

- At the end of the first cohort, a report will be developed and shared openly to

describe the process, successes, and opportunities for development and invite future collaboration.

Months 13-21 (WP-3-FS)

Objective: Offering services, including fiscal sponsorship infrastructure, to operationalise the new funding model in OLS (WP-3-FS)

1. Additional coaching and training will be provided as paid services, such as direct support for budgeting, legal compliance, community management, staff recruitment, etc.
2. Fiscal sponsorship will be offered to newly funded research projects

Outputs

- Timeline and strategy for fiscal sponsorship

Months 13-21 (WP-4-Research)

Objective: Research-based assessment of the project will be conducted (WP-4-Research)

Main objectives:

1. An impact research with the involvement of contributors and collaborators from the community will be conducted
2. Regular interaction with the project team and cohort members will be supported and maintained, updating them on the progress and inviting their participation

Outputs

- Initial impact research plans and reports from the assessment workshop were shared with the community
- Research outcomes will be reported in a scientific article (preprint)

Months 21-24 (WP-5-PM)

Objective: Reporting and strategy for scaling

- At this phase, the cohort will be wrapped up with the development of a project report and packaging of project outputs to be published openly
- Progress on the fiscal sponsorship will be assessed with recommendations for scaling over the next years
- Summary and findings from the cohort and research-based assessment of their impact will be developed to be shared openly

Outputs

- A report from the four packages will be developed
- Impact stories and future development plans will be shared
- Preprint from the project will be submitted for peer review

Capability to Deliver

About OLS

OLS (<https://we-are-ols.org/>, Open Life Science), is a skill and capacity-building organization that aims to overcome the challenges posed in traditional academia, sharing the benefits and impact of open science through a cohort and community-based approach. OLS believes that rigorous, robust, and responsible research can be achieved through open collaboration, reproducibility practices, research ethics, and EDI (equity, diversity, and inclusion), aiming to make all aspects of research open and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable). OLS nurtures these principles globally through its flagship program, Open Seeds.

Open Seeds is a 16-week training and mentoring initiative that employs a cohort-based approach to cultivate open science practices. Participants (individuals or teams) bring their projects or design new ones, applying open science and research best practices to make their work accessible to their communities. Since its launch in 2019, OLS has delivered eight cohorts of Open Seeds, supporting nearly 300 projects spanning various initiatives, from open data, code, resources, and events to establishing continental research collaboration platforms. All projects have been detailed on the organization's website: <https://openlifesci.org/openseeds/>. Open Seeds is internationally recognised and recommended for its cohort-based and community-supported approach. In contrast to other training programs, OLS's Open Seeds program also stands out for its project-based engagement and personalized mentorship. Participants not only learn about open science but also recognise the importance of community-based practices for scientific integrity, research innovation, research reproducibility, and open leadership across domains.

By prioritizing a community-first approach, the program has fostered international collaborations, publications, and research projects that extend its impact far beyond its direct reach, positively influencing thousands of researchers worldwide over the past five years. Since 2019, Open Seeds has engaged over 500 participants across 70+ countries, emphasizing the importance of inclusive communities in enhancing active involvement and leadership of diverse stakeholders in research. This proposal is essentially a need identified through feedback from the graduates from the Open Seeds who are leading important initiatives across the globe, but lack structured support and guidance in sustaining and sustaining through right funding.

Financial Sustainability with Training as a Service

OLS has become well-known in the open science ecosystem due to its high-quality training and mentoring programs coordinated and delivered by an expert program team. Additionally, engagement from a diverse network of experts across various research communities—many of whom have participated in OLS—has elevated OLS's reputation, consistently attracting new learners and experts to our initiatives. Particularly for Open Seeds, we have seen consistent demands for our training and mentoring since 2020. As shown in the data collected from eight cohorts of Open Seeds (https://openlifesci.org/ols-stats/openseeds/process_feedback.html), participants

report that OLS has helped them work openly, encouraged them to help others work in working openly, and apply open science practically in their work. Organizations, community initiatives and university-adjacent projects seeking to build skills and capacity in different aspects of research best practices in their organizations have enthusiastically collaborated with OLS. OLS has also secured service contracts, grants and partnership-based agreements to deliver training and mentoring as services as listed below.

OLS-9: two tracks, funded through grants and service-based contracts respectively

A 7-month service-based contract with 170,000 USD from [Digital Research Alliance Canada](#) was gained by OLS to embed Open Seeds in DRI-EDIA Champions Program. The DRI EDIA Champions Pilot Program aims to increase awareness and uptake of the Alliance's digital research infrastructure (DRI) by equity, diversity, inclusion, and accessibility (EDIA) champions across Canadian institutions. 90 fellows joining through this program will receive Open Seeds training and mentoring as part of their fellowship.

A parallel track of Open Seeds will be delivered as part of the CZI-funded [Catalyst Project](#) for the Catalyst community. This initiative aims to support the adoption of open science principles in underserved biomedical research communities by providing reliable and sustainable cloud computing infrastructure.

OLS-8: multi-organization supported program

The 8th cohort of Open Seeds was a result of collaboration with several graduates: a) a data community manager from VU Amsterdam who launched an open science champions program to support fellows in engaging with Open Seeds, while **partially covering the cost to deliver the cohort**; b) a data steward from TU Delft who supports PhD researchers to attend Open Seeds for **training credit recognised by the graduate program**; c) a technical consultant from a South African capacity building organization and a non-profit from Kenya to engage and **support their local networks of open science practitioners as part of service offered to universities**; and d) a Latin American training organization to learn about the infrastructure of Open Seeds to deliver cohort-based training through their collaboration with NASA.

This opportunity opened up new models for cohort-call-based budgeting that can be covered by multiple organizations interested in making Open Seeds training available in their network.

Paid services and funded projects that build on the cohort-based model

Leveraging the experience of moving cohorts through their upskilling and learning journey, OLS is expanding its service and scope to use the cohort-based and mentorship model with other organizations. For example, the Software Sustainability Institute has contracted OLS for four years to provide mentorship support for their fellows network.

OLS has also successfully received funding for three years from NASA-TOPS to expand the reach of NASA's Open Science 101 through OLS's "Nebula cohorts".

In-kind contributions have been made to support the development of cohort-based

training models in different organizations, such as the AI and Data Science Educators program at The Alan Turing Institute, the Turing-Roche Scholars Scheme, the Open Science fellowship by the eScience Center, and MetaDocencia's cohort-based training for NASA-TOPS

Leveraging OLS Partners and Funders Network

OLS's extensive network within the open science community represents practitioners and experts from international communities and organizations that include DRA Canada, IOI, CS&S, PreReview, Talarify, rOpenSci, RSE-Asia Associate, RSE-Australia New Zealand, zizc, Bioinformatics Hub Kenya, ELIXIR Europe, SSI, ReSA, NASA-TOPS, The Turing Way, Digital Research Academy, Creative Commons, FORRT, TU Delft, VU Amsterdam, Center for Rigor, MetaDocencia, Open Science Saudi Arabia and The Carpentries. Experts and collaborators will be invited from this network to contribute to this project.

Our funders and partners include the Software Sustainability Institute, Wellcome Trust, CZI, EOSC, SSI, ELIXIR, NASA, CS&S, and The Alan Turing Institute. Collaboration with these funders and philanthropic organizations is crucial for the success of this idea. Working closely with them, we can understand funding-related needs and requirements, enabling us to create the necessary support infrastructure for interested applicants together, especially from minority groups and LMICs from the earliest stages.

We have conceptualized and discussed this idea with key stakeholders from organizations such as the CZI Open Science Program, the Sloan Foundation, the Wellcome Trust Open Science team, UNESCO Open Science, members from GitHub, Google's Open Source Programs Office, and AWS Open Source.

About the Team

The OLS team proposing this plan includes the board of directors with Executive Director, Yo Yehudi, Director of Partnership, Malvika Sharan, Director of Technology, Bérénice Batut and Chief of Staff, Patricia Herterich.

Dr Malvika Sharan (PI on this proposal)

Malvika Sharan is a co-founder of OLS and the Director of Partnerships (part-time position). She is a Senior Researcher - Open Research at [The Alan Turing Institute](#). She is a co-lead of a community-led open source project [The Turing Way](#), lead of *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub funded under the InnovateUK Bridgeai program and lead of the [Open Research Community Management Team](#), working towards making data science a diverse, global and collaborative effort. With a PhD in Bioinformatics, Malvika is an alumna of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory. She is a Software Sustainability Institute fellow, a Mozilla Open Leader, an awardee of Cogx community leaders and JISC community champion awards, and has proudly made it to the 100 Brilliant Women in AI Ethics™ - 2024 list. Her previous contributions to open science initiatives include advisory and consultation roles for NASA TOPS, the Society of RSE, Open Bioinformatics Foundation, and MetaDocencia. You can often find her giving keynotes, talks and training at various open science events, conferences and workshops targeted at different stakeholders of research.

Dr Yo Yehudi

Yo is the Executive Director and co-founder of [OLS](#), a [Software Sustainability Institute Fellow](#), a NASA TOPS grantee, a Research Software Alliance Steering committee member, and [recently defended a doctoral thesis](#) studying human factors in research software and open communities. Previous roles include an editor for the [PLOS Open Source Toolkit](#), Codefirst: Girls coding instructor, Mozilla volunteer, editor emeritus for the [Journal of Open Source Software](#), board member of the [Open Bioinformatics Foundation](#), and a software developer working on an open source biological data warehouse called [InterMine](#), based at the University of Cambridge.

Dr Bérénice Batut

Bérénice Batut is a co-founder of OLS and the Director of Technology (part-time position). She is a Bioinformatics Engineer at the Institut Français de Bioinformatique: Évry-Courcouronnes in France. Bérénice has a PhD in computational biology from INSA Lyon, France. Previously in her role as a bioinformatician in the [Freiburg Galaxy Team](#), she focused on (metagenomic) biological data and data analysis tools via [Galaxy](#) and served as a co-deputy training coordinator for ELIXIR Germany node of [de.NBI](#). Bérénice is passionate about training and regularly gives talks and workshops (data analysis, tool development, etc). She is a co-founder and a co-lead of the [Galaxy Training Material project](#) and a founder of [Street Science Community](#), an outreach program.

Patricia Herterich

Patricia Herterich is OLS's Chief of Staff as well as an independent consultant. She holds an MA in Library and Information Science from Humboldt University of Berlin, Germany (2013) and has over ten years of experience in research data management and working on European-funded projects at CERN's Scientific Information Service and Higher Education institutions in the UK. She is a Software Sustainability Fellow 2019 and was an initial member of [The Turing Way](#) and [the Hidden REF](#) committee.